

"DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN PUBLIC EDUCATION".

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ABSTRACT

In our country, preschool education has become an integral part of the continuous education system. The development of this part of education is the result of consistent reforms in the field, where special attention is paid to the quality of educational services and the formation of the child's intellectual personality. This article talks about the modern approach to the development of preschool education.

INTRODUCTION. The President of the Republic's Decrees No. PQ-2707 of December 29, 2016 and No. PQ-3305 of September 30, 2017, both titled "On Organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan," and "2017 According to the regulation issued by the ministry of preschool education of the republic of uzbekistan, "quality preparation of children for education, strengthening the material and technical base of preschool educational organizations, expanding the state and non-governmental network of preschool educational organizations," "On measures to further improve the preschool education.

In preschool educational institutions governed by the Republic of Uzbekistan's Ministry Preschol Education, particular emphasis is currently placed on preparing kids for high-quality school education. The function of methodical support and methodical support in the entire development of the program were defined, in particular: 1. Application of the "First Step" program to the educational process. 2. Using the "First Step" curriculum as a foundation, special attention was given to the role of the educator in setup of centers and general group work across all age ranges.

Children will have the chance to voice their thoughts among their peers, make up stories based on the subject, ask questions, and lead dialogues for other children if we concentrate on the analysis of the activities in the centers, particularly in the language and speech center. The child can also write stories in the middle about whatever interests him. Speech development in children follows the development of their fine motor skills. Children can display their skills and talents in a very comfortable setting with story-role games and a dramatic center. This center may also be referred to as the child's "I" center. Every piece of

equipment in the center is something that kids use every day, and while playing the game, the kid learns how to use it and gets the chance to learn about other vocations. The game offers a chance to learn moral lessons while also giving educators a chance to research families and how family members interact with one another. Children are interested in and encouraged by experiments done at the Science and Nature Center's experimental testing area. The idea of the Republic of Uzbekistan's preschool education system being developed until 2030 was adopted, and it includes the following provisions:

- providing conditions for preschool children's holistic intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development; furthering the improvement of the normative legal framework in the field of preschool education;

- greater access to quality early education for all children and development of public-private partnerships in this area;

- introduction of innovations, cutting-edge pedagogical techniques, and information and communication technology into the system of preschool education;

- enhancement of the management system for early childhood education, which would ensure the effectiveness and openness of the financial operations of these institutions;

- adoption of wholly new methods for staff development, retraining, qualification enhancement, selection, and training in the preschool education system; ensuring healthy. An effective preschool education system was established during the recent time with the goal of supporting the formation of a rising generation that is healthy and fully developed.

Complicated organizational and legal procedures were also put into place. This percentage is projected to reach 59.5 percent in 2020, and 85.2 percent of 6-year-old children are expected to receive a year of compulsory schooling. To use cutting-edge management techniques for pre-school education, enhance the educational and training process, staff pre-school educational institutions with highly qualified professionals, and upgrade their physical plant, library collections, and technical apparatus,¹ Preschool education is not being provided in an acceptable manner by the Republic of Uzbekistan's Ministry of Public Education, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, and local state authorities.² It should be mentioned that new preschool educational institutions will be founded on January 1st in regional centers and the cities of Tashkent and Nukus as an experiment under the terms of a public-private partnership, including the following: random distribution of abandoned buildings, vacant lands, and non-operational state preschools. More than a year after the approval of the concept, a new law was adopted on the preschool education system, new projects and reforms are being implemented step by step. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 8, 2019 "On approving the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", this concept aims to further improve the preschool education system, ensure children's equal access to quality preschool education, and develop preschool education services. In a word, it covers the target tasks of the development of the preschool education system and defines the priorities and stages of the process. More than a year after the approval of the concept, a new law was adopted on the preschool education system, new projects and reforms are being implemented step by step. In particular, in 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Pre-School Education and Training" was adopted. In this Law, the main principles of pre-school education and training, directions of state policy in this field, as well as pre-school education under the ownership of

the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministry of Pre-School Education, the Ministry of Health the powers of state and economic management bodies and local state authorities, which are organizations, are defined. One of the key axes of the concept is to create environments that foster preschoolers' overall intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development. The gradual implementation of providing computers to preschool educational organizations and Internet connectivity aims to widely introduce innovations and advanced pedagogical, information, and communication technology in this system. If we take the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decision of May 8, 2019, "On approving the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," as an example, we can see that this concept seeks to further enhance the preschool education system, ensure children's equal access to high-quality preschool education, and develop preschool education services. It covers in a nutshell. The training, retraining, and capacity building of educators and administrative staff for preschool educational organizations have also seen favorable adjustments. One of the key axes of the notion is to provide the framework for preschoolers' total intellectual, moral, artistic, and physical development. The gradual implementation of providing computers to preschool educational organizations and Internet connectivity aims to widely introduce innovations and advanced pedagogical, information, and communication technology in this system.

Research Findings and Discussion In recent years, we have seen that the focus on preschool education, which is the most basic and smallest part of education, has risen to the level of public policy. In particular, to further improve the system of preschool education, strengthen the material and technical base, expand the network of preschool educational institutions, provide qualified teachers, radically improve the level of preparation of the younger generation for school education, comprehensive educational, pedagogical In order to create adequate conditions for aesthetic, physical and intellectual development, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021" Resolution No. 2707 was adopted. In accordance with the resolution, a number of important and urgent tasks have been identified, such as in-depth study of the system of preschool education in foreign countries, its implementation in our country and cooperation. This, of course, is very important for the education and upbringing of the younger generation, because we believe that the full study and implementation of the educational process in foreign countries will certainly pave the way for the introduction of more innovative and advanced practices. As in foreign countries, great changes are taking place in the system of preschool education in our country. In particular, the Concept of Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 will be the basis for the development of programs and comprehensive measures aimed at the development of preschool education. The document addresses the shortage of qualified teachers, the overcrowding of public institutions, the inadequacy of material and technical conditions, and the low level of provision of state educational materials. Meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on October 19 on "Issues of radical improvement of the preschool education system Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December, 29. In addition, systemic flaws inhibit the full execution of state policies in the area of preschool education, specifically:

First, the management of pre-school education at this moment does not allow for the timely

detection and removal of systemic issues, the creation and adoption of cutting-edge technology in this area, including the non-state sector;

The establishment of social and universal preschool educational institutions, their material and technical re-equipment, and the use of advanced pedagogical technologies have not been implemented, which brings us to our second point: public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at attracting investments in the field of preschool education have not been introduced.

Creating conditions for the all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development of preschool children is one of the main directions of the concept. In order to widely introduce innovations and advanced pedagogic and information and communication technologies in this system, provision of computers to preschool educational organizations and connection to the Internet are being implemented step by step. If we look at the example of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 8, 2019 "On approving the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", this concept aims to further improve the preschool education system, ensure children's equal access to quality preschool education, and develop preschool education services. In a word, it covers the target tasks of the development of the preschool education system and defines the priorities and stages of the process.

CONCLUSION. The past period has seen complex organizational and legal measures implemented to create an effective preschool education system. However, existing systemic deficiencies prevent the full implementation of state policy in the field of preschool education, such as the lack of timely identification and elimination of systemic problems, public-private partnership mechanisms, inadequate infrastructure and material and technical base, lack of personnel training and retraining, low financial incentive system, and shortcomings in the organization of regional health authorities' work on providing medical services to children in preschool educational institutions. Working in children's development centers prepares them for school education, loyalty, and interest.

References:

1. .O'zbekiston Respublikasining ilk va maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga qo'yiladigan "Davlat talablari". 2018-yil 3-iyul, ro'yxat raqami 3032.
2. . Mirziyoev Sh.M. "Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi" -T.:—O'zbekiston, 2021. 23-bet.
3. .Scientific Library of Uzbekistan Academic Research, Uzbekistan 503 www.uz
4. .<http://sdo-10.journal.ru/journalnumbers/anglijskaja-sistema-do.htm>
5. <http://razvivash-ka.ru/sistema-doshkolnogo-obrazovaniya-v-germani>.